

INTEGRATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING WITH CULTURE

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Annotation: *The article considers television as one of the most effective techniques in learning a foreign language and discusses its strengths and drawbacks in learning, focusing on the authenticity of the material and used tools for its more efficient use.*

Key words: *television, authentic, evidence based learning, audiovisual means, exploitability, purposeful context.*

After the proclamation of independence in 1991, the Republic of Uzbekistan concentrated its main attention to the reform of educational system, and in 1992 new "Law on Education" and "National Program of Training Personnel" were worked out where much prominence was given to mastering foreign languages of future specialists who should meet the requirements of both Uzbekistan and the world economy and policy. On the bases of the important official documents new state educational standards, syllabi, curricula, textbooks and methodological means of FLT were worked out for pre-school educational institutions (kindergartens), secondary schools, secondary specialized educational institutions (lyceums and professional colleges), higher education (institutes and universities) and others. The amount of time and content for FLT in them varies from one to another by specialty.

As Uzbekistan became fully open to the world many international collaborations on different spheres were settled, along with educational cooperation with developed countries. Different international educational grants, exchange programs, seminars and conferences, as well as branches of the world leading universities became available for pupils, students, teachers and researchers which brought to the influence of Western education on Uzbekistan.

Using and implementation of educational achievements of far and near foreign countries on teaching/learning languages in Uzbek education fitted requirements of modern Uzbekistan, as their experiences were proved by time and result.

Uzbek methodologists and linguists achieved to raise and solve very important scientific matters and all received practical and theoretical experiences were reflected and used while compiling of textbooks, methodological means and educational programs.

Modern foreign language teaching in the new Uzbekistan has adopted completely new methods. Active implementation of information and communication technologies in science and education has had a significant influence on the creation and development of innovative educational systems based on student-centered learning and solving problems. Modern society started to demand that a highly qualified expert must possess several foreign languages. The development of multilingual and multicultural linguistic identity has become particularly important in the modern world.

To meet the requirements of our rapidly evolving global society, education for the 21st century needs to be both interdisciplinary and cross-cultural. As foreign language teachers, our approach is to make language acquisition not an end, but a means for acquiring cultural information essential for communication.

The introduction of information technology in education varies in perception and mining information. Due to a computer, the Internet and multimedia, students have been given a unique opportunity to master large amounts of information with its subsequent analysis and sorting. The motivational basis of learning activity has been greatly extending. In the terms of multimedia, students started to receive information from newspapers, television, their own interviews and conduct space bridges.

It also should be noted that an important aspect in learning a foreign language is a communicative approach – a strategy that stimulates communication, aimed at creating a psychological readiness for language to communicate, on a conscious understanding of the material and the methods of working with it. Using the Internet in the communicative approach is the best motivated, its goal is to make students are interested in learning a foreign language through the accumulation and increase of their knowledge and experience. The use of the Internet technology in the classroom in a foreign language became one of the effective factors for the motivation of learners.

One of the innovative forms of organizing independent work of pupils/students is the project technology. The typology of the projects is varied. Although in actual practice one often has to deal with mixed projects, there are indications of research, creative, practice-oriented and

information projects. Work on the project is a multi-layered approach to language learning, covering reading, listening, speaking and grammar. Project-based learning promotes active independent thinking of students and directs them to the joined research work. In my opinion, the project training is actual because it teaches students cooperation, collaboration and learning such moral values as mutual support and empathy, generates creativity and activates learners. In general, in the process of project-based learning, there is the continuity of training and education.

The task of the development, improvement and optimization of methods of teaching foreign languages has always been one of the most pressing issues in education. The studies of pedagogical work in this field have shown that foreign language teaching today is impossible without the innovation component. In the light of modern requirements foreign language teaching has been changing the status of a student and a teacher who transferring from the scheme, "teacher - student" to student-centered technology training in close cooperation.

The communicative approach considers target language-based communicative competence to be essential in order for foreign language learners to participate fully in the target language culture. As such, the target language culture and its inhabitants, the native speakers, are elements crucial to the success of the teaching model. Learners are not only expected to acquire accurate forms of the target language, but also to learn how to use these forms in given social situations in the target language setting to convey appropriate, coherent, and strategically-effective meanings for the native speaker. Thus, learning a foreign language becomes a kind of enculturation, where one acquires new cultural frames of reference and a new world view, reflecting those of the target language culture and its speakers. Proponents of this view perceive foreign language teachers as 'gatekeepers' who equip their learners with the four competencies of communication with a view towards enabling them to gain access to educational or economic opportunities within the target language setting.

On a practical note, culture teaching started to allow Uzbek learners to increase their knowledge of the target culture in terms of people's way of life, values, attitudes, and beliefs, and how these manifest themselves or are couched in linguistic categories and forms. More specifically, the teaching of culture has made learners aware of speech acts, connotations, etiquette, that is, appropriate or inappropriate behaviour, as well as

provided them with the opportunity to act out being a member of the target culture.

II.2. Communicative Competence in teaching Foreign Language

The textbook is one of the main components of the methodical complete, which is functional, informative and organizational threads are associated with the other components of the educational environment. The highest the educational effect is achieved with the integrated use of all components in the completeness of not more than 15-17 students.

The textbook is built in accordance with the curriculum of the form (3 hours per week). Its lessons are developed basing on the plan. Reserve lessons can be used by a teacher accordingly on the following objectives: a) to finish what is left of time during scheduled classes, b) to perform a series of additional exercises corresponding to the individual interests of the students and to eliminate the achievement gap or more highest result of education and c) to hold, if necessary, terminal-control works, etc.

The content of the tutorial is aimed at giving the Uzbek students the opportunity to become better acquainted with the areas of the lives of British and American counterparts, what subjects they study, what are the rules of conduct exist in schools and how they are treated students as peers English-speaking countries spend their free time, the lessons are, what their interests and hobbies.

The content of texts in the textbooks started to emphasize on creating proper conditions for pupils to be able to communicate in the target language. The tasks and exercises began to be based on group or pair work, teachers often make students to be engage in role-paly or dramatization to adjust their use of the target language to different social contexts. Classroom materials are often authentic to reflect real-life situations and demands. Also the teacher's role has greatly changed, i.e. it is primarily to facilitate communication and secondarily to correct errors. All this served as a reflection of wide integration of the communicative approach.

The "communicative approach to the teaching of foreign languages" – also known as Communicative Language Teaching (CLT) or the "communicative approach" – emphasizes learning a language through genuine communication. Learning a new language is easier and more enjoyable when it is truly meaningful.

Communicative teaching is based on the work of sociolinguists who theorized that an effective knowledge of a language is more than merely

knowing vocabulary and rules of grammar and pronunciation. Learners need to be able to use the language appropriately in any business or social context.

Over the last three decades, theorists have discussed (and continue to discuss) the exact definition of communicative competence. They do agree, however, that meaningful communication supports language learning and that classroom activities must focus on the learner's authentic needs to communicate information and ideas.

Grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary are, of course, necessary parts of effective communication. With the communicative method two primary approaches may be taken. Some teachers prefer to teach a rule, then follow it with practice. Most, though, feel grammar will be naturally discovered through meaningful communicative interaction.

The communicative approach is a flexible method rather than a rigorously defined set of teaching practices. It can best be defined with a list of general principles. In *Communicative Language Teaching* (1991), expert David Nunan [17] lists these five basic characteristics:

1. An emphasis on learning to communicate through interaction in the target language.
2. The introduction of authentic texts into the learning situation.
3. The provision of opportunities for learners to focus, not only on language but also on the learning process itself.
4. An enhancement of the learner's own personal experiences as important contributing elements to classroom learning.
5. An attempt to link classroom language learning with language activities outside the classroom.

As these features show, the communicative approach is concerned with the unique individual needs of each learner. By making the language relevant to the world rather than the classroom, learners can acquire the desired skills rapidly and agreeably.

Using project methods in teaching a foreign language

In the European languages the word "project" is borrowed from Latin: the participle "projectus" means "thrown out forward", "striking one's eye". With reference to a lesson of foreign language, the project is specially organized by the teacher and independently carried out by pupils' complex of the actions, finished with creation of a creative product. A method of projects, thus, is the set of educational and cognitive modes which allow solving this or that problem as a result of independent actions of children with obligatory presentation of results.

Let's result some examples how to achieve at once at the lesson with the help of project methods the several purposes - to expand children's vocabulary, to fix the investigated lexical and grammatical material, to create at the lesson an atmosphere of a holiday and to decorate a cabinet of foreign language with colorful works of children.

The work with the projects teacher can realize in groups and individually. It is necessary to note, that the method of projects helps children to seize such competences as: to be ready to work in collective, to accept the responsibility for a choice, to share the responsibility with members of the team, to analyze results of activity.

The method of debates

It allows forming also the conscious attitude to consideration of problems, activity in its discussion, speech culture, an orientation on revealing of the reasons of arising problems and installation on their decision further. Here the principle of formation of critical thinking in pupils is realized. Language, thus, is simultaneously both the purpose and means of teaching. The method of debates helps pupils not only to seize all four kinds of speech activity, but to means of a language situation on a background of a problem in social and cultural sphere to find out the reasons of the arisen situations and to try even to solve them. Interest to the independent decision of a problem is the stimulus, driving force of process of knowledge.

Thus, application of a method of discussion allows making active cognitive activity of pupils, their independence, forms culture of creative operative thinking, creates conditions for use of personal life experience and received before knowledge for mastering new. As discussion and the decision of problems occurs during controlled group dialogue at participants skill to operate in interests of group is developed, there is an interested respect for interlocutors and conducts to formation of collective. Application of this method in aggregate with a method of projects will allow generating thinking and owning not only the English language, but also the expert understanding in various problems, capable to be guided in quickly varying information streams.

Not less interesting technique of activization of cognitive activity trained is the technique of role game which also can to reflect a principle of problematical character at its certain organization and allows to solve problem situations of a various degree of complexity. It can be used as independently, and in a context of a method of projects, is especial as the specific form of protection of the project. Trained apply the experience of

the saved up knowledge, results of research during work above the project in realization of socially significant roles growing on the importance with passage of a cycle of occupations. Such modeling of situations of professional - business intercultural dialogue helps pupil to get used to various situations of the future activity which he can face in a real life. Problematical character of role game is realized through modeling of situations in which this or that problem can find the certain decision. Being in a role, pupil solves problem situations, evidently showing in full communicative competence the practical decision of a problem. Certainly, such way of protection should be adequate to a researched problem. Selection by that and problems for use of this or that method - a separate research problem. Here it is important, that communicative competence was formed in real acts of intercourse in which the English language is means of formation and a formulation of idea. Thus, pupil, being based on the skills generated with the help of a debatable method, it is capable to apply and develop these skills in concrete situations of dialogue, carrying out socially significant roles and skill to assert the position in problem situations.

Games

The advantages of using games. Many experienced textbook and methodology manuals writers have argued that games are not just time-filling activities but have a great educational value. W. R. Lee holds that most language games make learners use the language instead of thinking about learning the correct forms. He also says that games should be treated as central not peripheral to the foreign language teaching programme. A similar opinion is expressed by Richard-Amato, who believes games to be fun but warns against overlooking their pedagogical value, particularly in foreign language teaching. There are many advantages of using games. Games can lower anxiety, thus making the acquisition of input more likely. They are highly motivating and entertaining, and they can give shy students more opportunity to express their opinions and feelings. They also enable learners to acquire new experiences within a foreign language which are not always possible during a typical lesson. Furthermore, they add diversion to the regular classroom activities, break the ice, but also they are used to introduce new ideas. In the easy, relaxed atmosphere which is created by using games, students remember things faster and better. Games are a good way of practicing language, for they provide a model of what learners will use the language for in real life in the future.

Games encourage, entertain, teach, and promote fluency. If not for any of these reasons, they should be used just because they help students see beauty in a foreign language and not just problems.

A foreign language teacher started to have many options in choosing a style to teach by. The teacher might write lesson plans of his own, borrow plans from other experienced teachers, or search online or within books for lesson plans. In deciding what teaching method to use, a teacher has had to consider his student's background knowledge, environment, and learning goals. A lesson plan might be carried out in several ways:

- Questioning: (similar to testing) the teacher asks a series of questions to collect information of what students have learned and what needs to be taught. He/she can test them on what was previously taught in order to identify if they have learned the material.
- Explaining: (similar to lecturing) in certain big classes, the teacher would be the only speaker, he gives a speech on a specific subject that is open to the public, usually in the classroom as there will be no enough time for every individual student to participate.
- Demonstrating: providing an opportunity in learning new exploration and visual learning tasks from a different perspective. It can be exercised in several ways. For instance, Microsoft PowerPoint is a program that allows the teacher put together a presentation to present to the class on a computer projector.
- Modeling: using visual aids, such as flash cards, video clips, cassette recorder, CDs, charts, maps, life objects, etc. students can visualize an object or problem, then use reasoning and hypothesizing to determine an answer.
- Collaborating: students' working in groups, it allows students talk among each other and listen to all view points of discussion or assignment. It helps them think in unbiased way.
- L by T: (learning by teaching), students take teachers' role and teach their peers (micro teaching).

The Process of learning has also changed:

Cooperative learning: It is a successful teaching strategy in which small teams, each with students of different levels of ability, use a variety of learning activities to improve their understanding of a subject. Each member is responsible not only for learning what is taught but also for helping teammates learn, thus creating an atmosphere of achievement. Students work through assignment until all group members successfully understand and complete it.

Cooperative efforts result in participants striving for mutual benefit so that all group members:

- Gain from each other's efforts.
- Recognize that all group members share a common fate.
- Feel proud and celebrate when a group member is recognized for achievement.

Cooperative learning is an approach to organizing classroom activities into social learning experiences. Students must work in groups to complete the set of tasks collectively.

- Jigsaw: it is a teaching technique used in small group instruction. Students of a normal-sized class (26-34 students) are broken into competency groups; each group is given a list of subtopics to research, with individual members of the group breaking off to work with the "experts" of other groups, then returning to their starting body in the role of instructor for their subcategory.

The main requirement for the FL textbook, especially for secondary education is very high that demands methodological competency. Many attempts were made to provide proper English textbooks and manuals for Uzbek secondary school after the proclamation of independency by teams of authors but we could observe in them poor methodology.

For example, series of school textbooks as "English Matters" and "Fly High" are very colourful, presentable and rich in themes that attract to some extent young language learners and follow cultural and communicative approaches, project based in content but they lack methodical sequence.

Although the English textbooks for the 10 – 11 forms created by known methodologist professor Jamol J. Jalolov that were widely used until 2009 are relevant to all methodical requirements in structure and content we can observe some merits and demerits in them: as merits we can underline that almost all texts, poems, songs, proverbs, saying etc. are authentic, i.e. they belong to either English or American culture. They provide very useful information that is linked with stylistics; as the demerits we can say that there are very few dialogues designed to develop pupils' interactive skills and pictures and photos are in black and white format.

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